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Alphabetical catalogue of Printed books: rules to be observed in preparing and entering titles [composed by Panizzi and presented to the Trustees on 18th March 1839].

ALPHABETICAL CATALOGUE

OF

PRINTED BOOKS.

RULES

TO BE OBSERVED

IN PREPARING AND ENTERING TITLES.

NUMBER IN THE
ILLUSTRATIONS.

133. 134. 169. 229.

102. 121.

38. 176.

132. 144. 156.

182. 186.

70. 200. 279.

148. 259.

4. 7. 22.

10. 252.

33. 51.

68. 209.

I. Titles to be written on slips, uniform in size.

II. Titles to be arranged alphabetically, according to the English alphabet only, whatever be the order of the alphabet in which a foreign name might have to be entered in its original language, under the surname of the Author, whenever it appears printed in the title, or [in any other part of the book. If the name be supplied in Ms. the work must nevertheless be considered anonymous or pseudonymous, as the case may be, and the Ms. addition deemed merely a suggestion to which the Librarian will attach such importance as he may think proper, on his own responsibility, in supplying the author's name between brackets, as hereafter directed] at the end of the dedication or preface, or in any other part of the work.

III. If more than one name occur in the title, by which it may appear that the work is the production of more than one person, the first name to be taken as that of the author. The reporter of a commission always to be considered the author of the report, although his name appear the last.

IV. The works of sovereigns, or of princes of sovereign houses, to be entered under their Christian or first name.

V. Works of Jewish Rabbis to be entered under their first name.

VI. Works of friars, who, by the constitution of their order, drop their surname, to be entered under the Christian name; the name of the family, if ascertained, to be added in brackets. The same to be done for persons canonized as well as for those known under their first name only, to which, to be distinguished, they add that of their native place, or profession, or rank. Patronymics derived from the ancestors or names of other persons, to be used as surnames.

VII. The respondent or defender in a thesis to be considered its author, except when in the title the authorship is unequivocally given to the Præses.

VIII. When an author uses a christian or first name only (either real or assumed) such name to be taken as a heading; and if more than one be used the first to be preferred for the principal

entry. The surname or family name when known to be added in brackets after the first name.

26. 76. 77. 79. IX. Assemblies or corporate bodies (with the exception of Academies, Universities and Learned Societies, respecting which special rules are to be framed,) to be considered as the authors of any act, vote, resolution, or other document purporting to be agreed upon, authorized or issued by them, no attention whatever being paid to the names of the officers who may have put their signature to such document.
- X. III. *In all instances in which variations may be found in the surname, peculiar to the same Author, it must be transcribed in that form, language, or peculiar orthography, in which it may happen to be expressed in the respective title pages in which it is recorded, as Grange, La Grange, De La Grange; Blanco, Blancus, Le Blanc, De Blanchis, Bianchi, White, &c.; Allciat, Alciato, Ailecyot, Alciatus, Alzatus, De Alzate, &c.*
104. 219. XI. Works of authors whose name may have been altered by being used in various languages, to be entered under the original vernacular form of the name.
49. 142. XII. Works of authors who change their name or add to it a second, after having begun to publish under the first, to continue to be entered under the first name, noticing any alteration which may have subsequently taken place.
120. 137. 274. XIII. Foreign names, excepting French, preceded by a preposition, an article, or by both, to be entered under the letter immediately following.
6. 3. 237. French names preceded by a preposition only, to follow the same rule; those preceded by an article, or by a preposition and an article, to be entered under the initial letter of the article. English
95. 96. 103. 159. 160. surnames, of foreign origin, to be entered under their initial, even if originally belonging to a preposition. Foreign compound surnames to be
37. 125. 183. 256. entered under the initial of the first of them. In
72. 242. compound Dutch and English surnames the last name to be preferred, if no entry of a work by the same person occur in the catalogue under the first name only.
133. 134. 137. 229. XIV. German names, in which the letters *ä*, *ö* or *ü* occur, to be spelt with the diphthong *ae*, *oe* and *ue* respectively.
52. 236. XV. IV. *Surnames of noblemen, though not expressed in the title, to be ascertained and written out as the heading of the title.*
183. 260. 269. XVI. The same rule to be followed with respect to Archbishops and Bishops.
215. XVII. V. *Christian names, included in brackets, (in parentheses) not [brackets], to follow the surname, and all to be written out in full, as far as*
218. *they are known. In case of doubt, a mark of interrogation to follow.*
- XVIII. VI. *Author's rank in society, in cases in which he enjoyed any eminent honorary distinction, as, Cardinal, Prince, Archbishop, Duke,*

6. Marquess, *Earl, and Bishop*, Count, Viscount,
 53. 85. *Baron, Baronet, Knight*, Admiral and General,
 &c., *to follow Christian name*, [to be stated] and
 to be underlined. *Titles of inferior rank, whether*
 32. 33. *ecclesiastical, military, or civil, to be given only*
when necessary to make a distinction between
authors having the same surname and christian
name.

XIX. VII. *The title of the book next to be*
written, and that expressed in as few words, and
those only of the author, as may be necessary to
exhibit to the reader all that the author meant to
convey in the titular description of his work; the
 64. 113. original orthography to be preserved. The num-
 34. ber of the edition to be stated when appearing in
 the title.

XX. If it be found unnecessary to transcribe the
 113. 134. 148. title at full length, and the omissions extend to
 more than a few insignificant words, dots to be
 144. 169. substituted to indicate the omission, more parti-
 cularly in old and rare volumes, in which, how-
 ever, abridgments should be seldom resorted to.

XXI. When the work is without a title-page, the
 64. 149. contents of the book to be concisely, but sufficiently,
 stated in the words of the head-title, (between
 parentheses,)—if there be no head-title in those of
 54. the colophon, (also between parentheses,)—and if
 this also be wanting or insufficient, then some idea
 223. 258. of the work to be briefly given in the language of
 the catalogue, [between brackets.]

XXII. Whenever one or more separate works are
 4. 80. mentioned in the title of any publication, as form-
 ing part of it, the same to be particularly noticed
 in entering the principal publication; and if not
 mentioned in the title page, but discovered to form
 220. part of the book when catalogued, this information
 to be added to the title between brackets or pa-
 rentheses, as the case may be.

XXIII. Works in any language but English,
 Latin, Italian, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Ger-
 man, Dutch, Danish, and Swedish, or their re-
 spective dialects, and not accompanied by a trans-
 lation in any of them, to be catalogued in the ori-
 3. 186. 192. 253. ginal title and characters, as far as possible, with
 the addition of an English translation, [in brackets],
 164. 169. should no version occur in the volume itself even
 of the title only; in case of any version of the
 title being given in one of the above mentioned
 languages, such version to be adopted.

XXIV. Works in more than one language, ac-
 242. companied by the original, to be entered in the ori-
 ginal only, if it be one of the above-mentioned lan-
 guages. If no original text occur, the first lan-
 guage used in the title to be preferred. In all
 cases the several languages used in the book to
 be indicated at the end of the title, in Italics.

XXV. Works with a title in a language dif-
 ferent from that used in the body of the book
 to be entered according to the above rule, merely
 144. 220. stating at the end of the title in Italics in what
 language the work is written.

XXVI. VIII. *The number of parts, volumes,*
fasciculi, or whatever may be the peculiar divi-

sions of each Author's work, to be next specified,
240. in the words of the title.

XXVII. When nothing is said in the title respecting this point, if a work be divided into several portions, but the same pagination continue, or, when the pages are not numbered, if the same register continue, the work to be considered as divided into parts; if the progressive number of the pages, or the register be interrupted, then each
21. series of pages or letters of the register to be designated as a volume.

XXVIII. IX. *Then the form, whether fol., 4to, 8vo, &c.; next the place, where the book was printed; and in particular cases, as in the in-*
18. 64. 220. *stance of early, or very eminent typographers, the Printer's name may be [to be] specified.*

XXIX. X. *The date to follow: when no date or place is specified in the printed book, then*
144. 220. *either or both may be [to be] given, if known to, or conjectured by, the Librarian; but in these instances they must be [to be] included in brackets.*

XXX. XI. *If an early printed book, and in*
144. 149. 221. *Gothic, or black letters, say in Lett. Goth, or B. L.; [the circumstance to be mentioned at the end of the title, thus:—G. L. or B. L.]*

XXXI. XII. *If printed on vellum or satin, or if an Editio princeps of a classical author, or if there are inserted any MS. notes, state these peculiarities.*

XXXII. If the author of the MS. notes be known, this information also to be added in italics
3. 20. [between brackets]. If the volume belonged to some very distinguished personage, the fact to be recorded in few words at the end of the entry, between brackets and in italics.

XXXIII. An editio princeps of a classical author to be distinguished by the letters E. P. at
220. 244. the end of the entry. Books with manuscript notes to be indicated by the letters M. N. at the
51. end of the title, previous to the size of the volume. Works printed on vellum to be distinguished by
220. 245. the words ON VELLUM in italic capitals at the end of the entry. The letters L. P. or F. P. in the same situation to point out copies on large, or fine paper.

XXXIV. XIII. *In case of Anonymous Works, some prominent or leading word in the title to be selected as the heading to be prefixed to the title. If the Author's name should be known or conjectured by the librarian, the same to be inserted at the end of the title, and included in brackets. Whenever no leading word can be fixed upon in the title of anonymous writings, the first word in the title, except it be an article or a preposition, may be taken, and the work entered alphabetically under it, adding, however, as many cross references as may be considered necessary from any other word.*

XXXV. When the author's name does not appear on the title, or in any other part of the work,

216. 281. the name of the editor (if there be any) to be used as a heading; or, if no editor's name appear, that
 64. of the translator, if there be one, if not, any other name of a person or office appearing on the title
 44. 53. 132. (except that of the person to whom the book is merely dedicated) to be preferred. If no such name appear, that of any assembly, corporate
 217. body, society, board, party or sect, and if no such
 116. name, that of any country, province, city, town or place to be preferred. If two names occur seeming
 180. to have an equal claim, the first to be chosen.
 151. Reporters to be considered as editors.

1. 2. 123. XXXVI. Works published under initials, to be entered under the last of them; and should the librarian be able to fill up the blanks left, or complete the words which such initials are intended to represent, this to be done [and all the supplied parts to be included between brackets].

121. 124. XXXVII. In the case of anonymous works, to which none of the foregoing rules can be applied, the first substantive in the title (or if there be no
 157. 258. 277. substantive, the first word) to be selected as the heading. Should the author's name be known to or
 34. 121. 281. conjectured by, the librarian, the same to be inserted at the end of the title [between brackets].

XXXVIII. Works without the author's name, and purporting to comment or remark on a work of which the title is set forth in that of such publication, to be catalogued under the same heading as the work remarked or commented upon.

XXXIX. XIV. *In the case of Pseudonymous Publications, the book to be catalogued under the Author's feigned name; and his real name, if discovered, to be inserted in brackets, at the conclusion of the title, immediately after the feigned name; preceded by the letters i. e.*

155. 212. XL. Assumed names to be treated as real names. Academical names to follow the same rule.

201. XLI. Works falsely attributed in their title to a particular person, to be treated as pseudonymous.

164. XLII. Works of several writers, collectively published, to be entered according to the following rules, and the separate pieces of the various authors included in the collection to be separately entered in the order in which they occur; excepting
 114. merely collections of letters, charters, short extracts from larger works and similar compilations.

XLIII. XV. *In any long series of printed works, which embraces the collected productions of various writers upon particular subjects, such as Ugolini Thesaurus Antiq. Sacrarum, Gronovii Thesaurus Antiq. Græcarum, the work to be entered under the name of the Editor.*

XLIV. If the editor's name do not appear

210. the whole collection to be entered under the collective title, in the same manner as anonymous works.

XLV. General collections of laws, edicts, ordinances or other public acts, embracing more than one reign or duration of power in the same chief of the state, to be entered under the name of the state in which they were sanctioned, signed or promulgated, if no editor's name appear in any part of the collection; should the editor's name appear the general rule respecting collections to be followed. Collections extending only to one reign or period of supreme government by one person, as well as detached laws and documents separately enacted and issued, to be entered under the name of the person in whose name, and by whose authority they are enacted or sanctioned.

XLVI. *XVI. The Works of Translators to be entered under the name of the original Author.*
 20. 21. *The same rule to be observed with respect to the Works of Commentators, if the same, be accompanied with the text complete.*

XLVII. Translations to be entered immediately after the original, generally with only the indication of the language into which the version has been made, in italics; but if any material alteration in the title have been introduced, so much of the title of the translation to be given as may be deemed requisite, or a short explanation in the language of the catalogue added [between brackets].

XLVIII. Commentaries unaccompanied by the text, to be entered under the commentator's name; if without a name, or with an assumed name, then according to the rules laid down for anonymous or pseudonymous works.

XLIX. No work ever to be entered twice at full length. Wherever requisite, cross references to be introduced.

L. Cross references to be divided into two classes; from name to name, and from work to work; the former to contain merely the name, title, or office of the person referred from, and the surname or name of the person referred to as entered; the latter, so much of the title besides, as, together with the size and date, may give the means of at once identifying, under its heading, the book referred to, as well as the object of the reference.

LI. Cross references of the first class to be made in the following instances:

From the titles of noblemen, the sees of archbishops or bishops, the designation of any office or dignity, to the family name, or the first name under which the works of such personages are to be entered according to the foregoing rules.

LII. From the family name of persons whose works are to be entered under the Christian or first name, to such Christian or first name; excepting the case of sovereigns, or princes belonging to sovereign houses.

23. 27. 73. 219. LIII. From any surnames either spelt, or in any way used, in a manner differing from the one adopted in the principal entry, to such entry.

93. 162. 213. LIV. From any of the names or surnames used by an author besides the one under which the principal entry is made, to the one so preferred.

283. LV. From the real to the assumed name of authors; adding *pseud.* to the entry referred to in the cross reference.

LVI. Cross references of the second class to be made in the following instances:

199. 271. From the names of editors, commentators, annotators, biographers, who have prefixed an author's life to his works, translators, engravers, 58. 243. illustrators, authors, who have shared with another in writing a work, or have continued it, or in cases parallel to any of those here mentioned. 126. 133.

102. 254. LVII. From the name of authors of anonymous works supplied in the principal entry, to such entry.

184. 228. LVIII. From the name of any person the subject of any biography or narrative, to its author; stating briefly, in italics, after the name referred from, the peculiar designation of the biography in the work referred to; or, if this cannot be done, using the nearest English word [in brackets and italics] that may give an idea of the object of the cross reference.

LIX. From any name which from any cause 57. whatever may be reasonably conceived to have an equal claim to that selected for the principal entry, to such entry.

177. LX. From any author, any whole work of whom or any considerable part of it, may be the subject of a commentary, notes, &c., to the name of the commentator, annotator, &c. No notice to be taken of the name of authors, fragments, or inconsiderable parts of whose works are descanted upon by the commentator, annotator, &c.

146. 153. LXI. From any author whose works, or considerable part of them contained in a collection, are considered so important as to be distinctly specified in the entry of the collection itself, to the principal entry; the volume, or part of the collection in which the article so referred to is found, to be specified.

LXII. From the names of authors whose entire works or any considerable part of them are included among the collected works of a polygraphic writer, or translator, to the principal entry.

131. 214. LXIII. From the name of a state to which a collection of laws, bearing the name of an editor, belongs, to the name of such editor.

LXIV. Entries to be made in the following order;

Cross-references to be placed at the beginning of the entry, from which they are made, in the alphabetical order of the entries referred to.

LXV. Collections of all the works of an author

in their original language only, to be entered immediately after the cross-references; the editions without date, and those of which the date cannot be ascertained even by approximation, to precede all those bearing date, or of which the date can be supplied either positively or by approximation. The latter to follow according to their date, whether apparent in any part of the book, or supplied. Editions by the same editor, or such as are expressly stated to follow a specific text or edition, and editions with the same notes or commentary, to succeed each other immediately in their chronological order after the entry of that which is, or is considered to be, the earliest.

LXVI. The text of the collected works, accompanied by a translation, to be entered in the same order as the text only.

LXVII. The translations of such collected works into the Latin language only to precede those in any other language in the above order; the Latin translations to be followed by those in English. Translations in any other language to follow according to alphabetical order of the name of the language in English. If the volume contain two or more translations, without the text, the entry to be made according to the alphabetical order of the first of the languages employed. Translations in the same language, and their several editions, to be entered in conformity with the rules laid down for the entries of the originals.

LXVIII. Collections of two or more works of an author to be entered in the order and according to the rules laid down for the collections of all the works of a writer; such partial collections to precede, as are known or are supposed to contain the largest number of an author's works.

LXIX. Selections, or collected fragments, from the works of an author, to follow the partial collections of his works, and to be entered according to the above rules.

LXX. Separate works of an author to succeed each other alphabetically; the several editions and translations of each of them to be entered in the same manner as directed for the collected works of a writer.

LXXI. Entire fragments of a separate work to succeed the work from which they are taken, in the order above directed. If the whole work to which they belong do not occur, such fragments to be entered after all the separate works, but according to the principles laid down for the latter.

LXXII. Works not written by the person under whose name they are to be catalogued, according to the foregoing rules, to be entered alphabetically and in chronological succession, when more than one article occurs in the same alphabetical series, after all the works of the person whose name is selected, if any occur in the catalogue. Volumes without date, or the date of which cannot be supplied, to be entered first.

LXXIII. The same rule as to the alphabetical and chronological arrangement to apply to works entered under any other heading than the name of a person.

ILLUSTRATIONS.

1. A., D. J. B. DE. Coleccion de algunos versos de D[on] J[uan] B[autista] de A[rriaza]. 12° Paris, 1805.
2. A., D. S. F. D. Risposta et trattato delle ragioni della regina cristianissima sopra il Ducato del Brabante et altri stati della Fiandra, &c. D[el] S[ignor] F[rancesco] D['] A[ndrea]. 4° Napoli, anno 1667 e 1676.
3. ABEN-SINA, or AVICENNA. كتاب القانون في الطب لابو علي الشيخ ارييس ابن سينا مع بعض تاليفه وهو علم المنطق وعلم الطبيعى وعلم الكالم [The Book of the Canon of Physic by Abu Ali Al Sheikh al Riis Aben-Sina, with additions; namely, the Science of Logic, the Science of Nature, and the Science of Rhetoric.] Arab. fol. Romæ, 1593. [With manuscript notes, (by Casaubon?) one of which is as follows: "JACOBI AUGUSTI THUANI viri incomparabilis Isaaco Casaubono κειμενων."]
 4. ADRIANO [CASTELLESI?], *Cardinale*. De sermone Latino et modis Latine loquendi. Ejusdem Venatio ad Ascanium Cardinalem. Item, Iter Julii II. Pont. Rom. 8° Parisiis, 1528.
 5. AGRICULTURE, *Board of*. Account of the experiments tried by the Board of Agriculture in the composition of various sorts of bread, anno 1795. 4° London, 1795.
 6. AGUESSEAU (HENRI FRANÇOIS D'), *Chancelier de France*. Œuvres; 13 tom. 4° Paris, 1759—1789.
 7. ALBERTANO, *Giudice*; or ALBERTANUS, *Causidicus Brixienis*. Tre trattati: Il primo della dilezion d'Iddio, e del prossimo, e della forma dell'onesta vita: il secondo della consolazione e de' consigli: il terzo delle sei maniere del parlare. 4° Firenze, 1610.
 8. ALEMBERT (JEAN LEROND D'). Œuvres philosophiques, historiques et littéraires; 16 tom. 8° Paris, an XIII. (1805).
 9. ANDREA (FRANCESCO D'). v. A., D. S. F. D.
 10. ANDREÆ (JOANNES). Summa super quarto decretalium. 4° [Colonia, Henricus Quentell. B. L.]
 11. ANGLURE (— D'), *la Marquise*. v. TARGET (GUI-JEAN-BAPTISTE). Consultation. 8° 1787.
 12. ANSTEY (CHRISTOPHER). v. BATH. New Bath Guide. 8° 1767.
 13. ANTHONINUS; or ANTONINUS, *Sanctus, Archiepiscopus Florentinus*. (Tractatus de instructione seu directione simplicium confessorum. Editus a domino Anthonino archiepiscopo Florentino). 4° [Colonia, Joannes Guldenschaff, 1477? G. L.]
 14. AQUINAS (THOMAS), S. v. THOMAS, S.
 15. ARATUS, *Solensis Ciliæ*. v. LECTIUS (JACOBUS). Poetæ Græci veteres. fol. 1606.
 16. ARISTOTELES. Poetica. Gr. fol. Basilea, 1531.
 17. ————— 12° Basilea, 1537.
 18. ————— 8° Parisiis, apud Gulielmum Morelum, 1555.
 19. ————— Lat. per Theod. Goulstonum. 4° Londini, 1623.
 20. ————— Engl. with notes on the Translations and on the original, and two dissertations on poetical and musical imitations, by Tho. Twining. [With M.N. by Dr. Burney.] 4° London, 1789.
 21. Aristotelis Organum; hoc est, libri omnes ad Logicam pertinentes, Græcè et Latinè. Julius Pacius recensuit atque ex libris cum manuscriptis tum editis emendavit: e Græca in Latinam linguam convertit: Editio secunda Accessit ejusdem Pacii in universum Organum (et in Porphyrii Isagogen) Commentarius Analyticus. [2 vols.] 4° Francofurti, 1597.
 22. ARNALDUS, or ARNOLDUS, *de Villanova*. Opera nuperrime revisa: una cum ipsius vita (à Symphoriano Campegio edita) recenter hic apposita. Additus est etiam tractatus de philosophorum lapide intitulatus. fol. Lugduni, 1520.
 23. ARNOLDUS *de Villanova*. v. ARNALDUS.
 24. ARRIAZA (JUAN BAUTISTA). v. A., D. J. B. DE.
 25. As you find it, a Comedy. [By Charles Boyle, Earl of Orrery.] 4° London, 1703.
 26. ASSEMBLEE NATIONALE *Constituante, de France*. Decret de l'Assemblée Nationale sur la contribution foncière, des 20, 22 et 23 Novembre, 1790. 8° [Paris,] 1790.
 27. AVICENNA. v. ABEN-SINA.
 28. BAIRD (GEORGE). v. BATEMAN (THOS.), *M.D.* Disputatio medica. 8° 1801.
 29. BARCA (PEDRO CALDERON DE LA). v. CALDERON DE LA BARCA.

30. BARRUEL DE BEAUVERT (ANT. JOS.), *Comte*. Vie de J. J. Rousseau. 8° Londres, [Paris] 1789.
31. BARTOLOMEO (PAOLINO DA SAN). v. PAOLINO.
32. BATEMAN (THOS.). A treatise on agistment tithe. 2d Edit. 8° London, 1778.
33. BATEMAN (THOS.) *M.D. Resp.* Disputatio medica inauguralis de Hæmorrhæa Petechiali. Præs. Georgio Baird. 8° Edinburgi, 1801.
34. BATH. The new Bath guide; or, memoirs of the B[a]r[nar]d family. In a series of poetical epistles. [By Christopher Anstey.] The fifth Edition. 8° London, 1767.
35. BATH, *Abbey Church of*. v. SALISBURY, *Cathedral Church of*. The history, &c. 8° 1723.
36. BATH AND WELLS (JAMES), *Bishop of*. v. MOUNTAGUE.
37. BAUMGARTEN-CRUSIUS (LUD. FRID. OXON.). Opuscula theologica. 8° Jena, 1836.
38. BEAUMONT (FRANCIS), and FLETCHER (JOHN). Comedies and Tragedies written by F. B. and J. F., Gentlemen: never printed before, and now published by the authours' original copies. fol. London, 1647.
39. BEAUVERT (ANT. JOS. BARRUEL DE). v. BARRUEL DE BEAUVERT.
40. BECHE (HENRY T. DE LA). v. DE LA BECHE.
41. BELLINGHAM (JOHN). v. HODGSON (THOMAS). Trial of J. B. 8° 1812.
42. BERRIMAN (WILLIAM). v. FAMILY RELIGION. Family religion recommended. 8° 1735.
43. BETHA VON REUTIN. v. ELIZABETH, *Saint*.
44. BLACKALL (OFFSPRING), *Bishop of Exeter*. A Vindication of the Lord Bishop of Exeter [Offspring Blackall]; occasioned by Mr. Benjamin Hoadly's reflections on his Lordship's two Sermons of Government, preached March 8, 1704, and March 8, 1708. 8° London, 1709.
45. BOIS (L. J. J. DU). v. DUBOIS.
46. BOLINGBROKE (HENRY), *Viscount*. v. SAINT-JOHN.
47. BOYLE (CHARLES), *Earl of Orrery*. v. As you find it. 4° 1703.
48. BROWNISTS. The Brownists' Conventicle; or, an assembly of Brownists, Separatists, and Non-conformists, &c. 8° London, 1641.
49. BUCHANAN, afterwards HAMILTON (FRANCIS). A journey from Madras through the countries of Mysore, Canara, and Malabar; 3 vols. 4° London, 1807.
50. An account of the fishes found in the river Ganges and its branches. 4° Edinburgh, 1822.
51. BUERCKLIN (GEORGIUS CHRISTIANUS), *Resp. Ex ovopocari xvgiso Iragov*. Disputatio de Linguarum, Teutonicæ, Latine, Græcæ atque Ebrææ addiscendarum facili ratione. Præs. J. H. Majo. [M. N.] 4° Gissa-Hassorum, 1693.
52. BUTLER (JAMES), *Duke of Ormond*. The conduct of the D. of O. in the campagne of 1712. 4° London, 1715.
53. BYNG (*Hon.* JOHN), *Admiral*. A letter to a member of Parliament in the country from his friend in London, relative to the case of Admiral B., with some original papers. 8° London, 1756.
54. CALDERINUS (DOMITIUS), (Commentarii in M. Valerium Martialem.) 4° Romæ, per Magistrum Johannem Genszberg, 1474.
55. CALDERON DE LA BARCA (PEDRO). Comedias que nuevamente corregidas publicó Don Juan de Vera Tassis y Villarroel; 9 pts. 4° Madrid, 1726 and 1698.
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